

Comparison Study on Removal of Fluoride in Groundwater using Boron-doped and Non-doped Activated Carbon Prepared from Indian Kino tree (*Pterocarpus marsupium*)

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ABSTRACT

Elevated fluoride concentrations in drinking water are recognized as a public health concern due to their potential to cause a range of dental disorders upon prolonged ingestion. The objective of this study was to assess the amount of fluoride removed from groundwater using activated carbon made from Indian Kino tree or Malabar Kino tree (*Pterocarpus marsupium*) sawdust, both doped and non-doped with boron. The adsorbents were investigated under varying experimental conditions including temperature, agitation speed, adsorbent dosage, and particle size. The non-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon served as the control group in this study, with 20 samples, and boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon represented the experimental group, also with 20 samples. The results indicated that the boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon achieved a maximum fluoride removal efficiency of 97.5%. In comparison, the non-doped activated carbon reached a slightly lower efficiency of 94% under optimized conditions (Run 4), which involved a particle size of 600 μm , an adsorbent dosage of 4 g, an agitation speed of 450 rpm, and a temperature of 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. These results confirmed the efficacy of both materials, with boron doping providing an enhanced fluoride adsorption capability. Statistical analysis yielded a significant p-value of 0.013 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the difference in removal efficiency between the two groups was statistically significant. Overall, the findings indicated that boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium*-derived activated carbon offered improved fluoride remediation potential, making it a promising candidate for addressing fluoride contamination in groundwater and reducing associated dental health risks.

Keywords: Adsorption Efficiency; Biomass-Derived Adsorbents; Boron Modification; Defluoridation; Water Purification.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fluoride contamination in groundwater is a significant global environmental and public health issue. While fluoride is essential for dental and skeletal health in trace amounts, excessive intake

can lead to detrimental health effects such as dental and skeletal fluorosis. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends a fluoride concentration limit of 1.5 mg/L in drinking water.

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However, in many regions, especially in arid and semi-arid areas, fluoride levels exceed this limit due to natural and anthropogenic factors, necessitating effective fluoride removal techniques (Damtie *et al.*, 2019; Wan *et al.*, 2021). Fluoride pollution can be brought on by both natural and artificial sources, much like any other type of pollution (Shaji *et al.*, 2024). Fluoride is considered one of the most hazardous elements since fluoride ions are prevalent in groundwater and leach from fluorospar rock resources (Lubojanski *et al.*, 2023). The concentration of fluoride ions determines their dangerous effects. If the fluoride content is higher than 1.5 mg/L, young children typically experience dental problems and discoloured teeth (Tiwari *et al.*, 2023). If the groundwater has more fluoride than this, it must be treated to below the 1.5 mg/L level before consumption (Tanwer *et al.*, 2023). Skeletal fluorosis has been linked to groundwater fluoride concentrations greater than 3.2 mg/L (Keesari *et al.*, 2021). Treating groundwater with activated carbon reduced the fluoride concentration to 0.3 mg/L (Bakhta *et al.*, 2022); however, excessively low fluoride levels below the optimal range of around 0.7 mg/L are also undesirable, as they may increase the risk of dental caries (O'Malley *et al.*, 2025).

Paikaray and Chander (2022) examined groundwater geochemistry in Fazilka, a predominantly agricultural district located in the south-western part of Punjab, India, near the India–Pakistan border, where serious fluorosis concerns were reported due to high fluoride contamination of groundwater used for drinking water purposes. Fluoride concentrations in Fazilka's groundwater are much higher than those found in surface water and range from 6 to 12 mg/L, significantly exceeding both national and international permissible limits (Paikaray and Chander, 2022). Prolonged exposure to such high fluoride levels has led to a dental decay rate of approximately 70% among the local population,

underscoring the urgent need for implementing effective defluoridation strategies in the area. Fluoride is removed from groundwater using a wide range of treatment methods, including coagulation, membrane filtering, ion exchange, electrochemical oxidation, and electrocoagulation. The adsorption process is regarded as the most practical, long-lasting, and environmentally benign of these techniques. Activated carbon filtration, which is generally believed to combine ion exchange and physical adsorption, is considered the most effective method for removing fluoride (Panhwar *et al.*, 2024). Neutral and acidic sulfate-containing solutions reduce activated carbon capacity regarding fluoride adsorption (Turki *et al.*, 2023). Activated carbon adsorption recently gained prominence with regards to groundwater defluoridation, due to rapid equilibrium attainment (approximately 20 minutes) (Thomas *et al.*, 2023). This study adopts methodological approaches established by previous investigations (Turki *et al.*, 2023; Thomas *et al.*, 2023; Sivakumar *et al.*, 2018), ensuring comparability and validity of results. According to Google Scholar, approximately 225 studies, and as per Science Direct, 80 studies have examined the removal of fluoride using different adsorbents in the past five years. This indicates a growing global research interest in developing efficient, low-cost, and sustainable adsorbent-based technologies for fluoride removal, highlighting the urgency and relevance of addressing fluoride contamination in drinking water.

Extensive research has explored various materials and techniques for fluoride removal. Advanced cellulose-, polymer-, and graphene-based membranes have shown promise, with hydrophilicity and ion selectivity being critical to performance (Tolkou *et al.*, 2021a). Graphene-enhanced membranes further improved efficiency due to superior mechanical strength and chemical stability (Tolkou *et al.*, 2021a). Zeolites modified

with metal ions significantly increased fluoride adsorption, as supported by kinetic and isotherm analyses (Turki *et al.*, 2023). Nanomaterials such as graphene oxide and composite adsorbents supported on activated carbon exhibited high fluoride removal due to their reactive surfaces and tunable structures (Chufa *et al.*, 2022; Patel and Bhasin, 2023). Other techniques include electrocoagulation and photocatalysis, which offer innovative fluoride removal mechanisms. Electrocoagulation has been evaluated for cost-effective drinking water treatment (Castañeda *et al.*, 2021), and visible-light photocatalysis has emerged as a novel oxidative process (Lin *et al.*, 2021). Natural and modified low-cost adsorbents also show potential: diatomite modified with aluminium hydroxide and hydroxyapatite-modified shell powder performed effectively in fluoride removal, particularly in resource-limited settings (Akafu *et al.*, 2019; Yapo *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, zirconium-impregnated anion exchange resins and composite adsorbents synthesized from various materials displayed notable adsorption capabilities (Singh *et al.*, 2020; Wei *et al.*, 2022).

Several studies have explored the use of activated carbon and its modifications for effective fluoride removal from water. Previous research has utilized various bio-adsorbents for fluoride removal from groundwater and alleviating dental symptoms. However, these studies did not utilize activated carbon doped or non-doped with boron derived from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust (Akafu *et al.*, 2019; Ogata *et al.*, 2020). The main objective of this research is to discover new materials that can remove contaminants, including fluoride from groundwater. Previous treatment techniques showed a lower proportion of fluoride removal from groundwater. Another goal of this study is to incorporate boron into activated carbon made from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust to enhance bio sites, with both forms targeting fluoride removal. Activated carbon, a commonly used adsorbent, has shown promise in

contaminant removal due to its high surface area, porous structure, and customizable properties. Recent advancements include doping activated carbon with elements like boron to enhance adsorption capacity and selectivity towards fluoride ions (Pillai *et al.*, 2020; Patel and Bhasin, 2023).

This study aims to investigate and compare the efficiency of boron-doped and non-doped activated carbon derived from *Pterocarpus marsupium* in removing fluoride from groundwater. The choice of *Pterocarpus marsupium*, a sustainable and readily available biomass, aligns with the growing emphasis on environmentally friendly and cost-effective water treatment solutions. Modifying activated carbon with boron introduces new adsorption mechanisms that could potentially enhance fluoride uptake capacity and provide a competitive edge over traditional adsorbents (Ogata *et al.*, 2020; Akafu *et al.*, 2019). Bakhta *et al.* (2022) synthesized functional activated carbon and demonstrated its efficacy in reducing groundwater fluoride concentrations, showcasing high adsorption capacity and practical applicability. Patel and Bhasin (2023) developed a graphene/cerium (Ce) composite supported on activated carbon, exhibiting enhanced fluoride adsorption performance due to the synergistic effects of the composite materials. Thomas *et al.* (2023) investigated aluminum-modified activated carbon, reporting efficient fluoride removal and favorable adsorption behavior, supporting its use in groundwater remediation. Sivakumar *et al.* (2018) focused on nickel removal from industrial wastewater using bamboo-based activated carbon contributing valuable knowledge on activated carbon development and its potential in heavy metal and ion removal, including fluoride. These studies collectively confirm that activated carbon, especially when modified or composited with other materials, remains a promising and effective adsorbent for fluoride removal from aqueous systems.

While various modified adsorbents and nanocomposites have shown improved fluoride removal efficiency, such as aluminium hydroxide-coated diatomite (Akafu *et al.*, 2019), hydroxyapatite-modified shell powder (Yapo *et al.*, 2022), and zirconium-based resins (Singh *et al.*, 2020), none of these studies focused on boron-doped activated carbon derived from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust. Additionally, while recent studies (Bakhta *et al.*, 2022; Patel and Bhasin, 2023; Thomas *et al.*, 2023) reported success using advanced carbon-based materials, a direct comparison between boron-doped and non-doped forms of activated carbon from this specific biomass under controlled conditions has not been conducted. The statistical significance of such a comparison also remains underexplored. This study uniquely develops and compares boron-doped and non-doped activated carbon synthesized from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust for fluoride remediation. It introduces boron doping as a strategy to enhance adsorption efficiency through improved surface properties and affinity toward fluoride ions. The use of a sustainable, underutilized biomass source, along with a controlled experimental design and statistical evaluation, distinguishes this work from prior research and supports the development of cost-effective, eco-friendly water treatment technologies. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the efficiency of fluoride removal from groundwater using activated carbon derived from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust, both doped and non-doped with boron.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study Area

This study was conducted in Thiruvallur, located in Thiruvallur District, Tamil Nadu, India (13.14°N latitude and 79.91°E longitude). The region has a tropical climate, with an average annual temperature of 28°C and mean annual precipitation of approximately 1,200 mm, primarily during the northeast monsoon. In Thiruvallur district, fluoride concentrations in

several groundwater sources exceeded permissible limits, with levels reaching up to 2.7 mg/L in Thiruvallur town, likely due to leaching from mineral-rich rocks (Muththamizh *et al.*, 2023). As a result, five representative groundwater samples from different locations within Thiruvallur town were collected and assessed for fluoride concentration levels, following the procedures of the American Public Health Association (APHA Standard Methods, 2017). The results indicated an average fluoride concentration of 3.6 mg/L, significantly exceeding the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) permissible limit of 1.5 mg/L for drinking water (IS 10500:2012), highlighting the urgent need for efficient fluoride removal interventions in the region.

Various characteristics of groundwater from different sites were examined to determine its suitability for drinking (Sivakumar *et al.*, 2018). However, this analysis focused more on fluoride in groundwater than other ions. The groundwater samples were collected in airtight bottles, transported to the environmental laboratory for storage at a temperature of 5°C to avoid contamination, and later used for testing.

2.2. Preparation and Chemical Activation of Activated Carbon

Indian Kino tree or Malabar Kino tree (*Pterocarpus marsupium*) grows up to a height of 31 m and is locally referred to as *Vengai*. This is the starting material needed to extract fluoride. From the wood chips of *Pterocarpus marsupium*, saw dust was prepared for the production of non-doped activated carbon. The saw dust was sieved to obtain the desired particle size and then dried for 16 hours at 400°C in a hot air oven to produce activated carbon. After cooling to room temperature, this non-doped activated carbon was collected and stored for use in experiments.

Chemical activation was carried out using boric acid with a portion of this non-doped activated carbon by mixing 10 g of dried activated carbon with 100 ml of boric acid and heating at 85°C for

three hours in a hot air oven, followed by drying at 110°C to produce boron-doped activated carbon. After cooling to room temperature, the boron-doped samples were stored in sealed plastic containers and used in experiments.

2.3. Adsorption Study

In the adsorption study, two groups were involved, the control group (group 1 – N=20) consisted of non-doped boron novel *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon as the control group (group 1 - Number of samples, N=20) and boron-doped novel *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon. Instead of conducting 625 trials for each group using a full factorial design with 4 parameters at 5 levels, this study adopted the Box–Behnken experimental design, which reduced the experiment runs to 20 per group for both non-doped and boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon powders (Sivakumar, 2021). In this study, fluoride is removed from groundwater against various process parameters: particle size of 600, 500, 425, 300 and 150 µm, adsorbent dosage of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 g per liter, agitation speed of 150, 250, 350, 450 and 550 rpm, and

groundwater temperature of 35°C, 40°C, 45°C, 50°C and 55°C. For the experiments, one litre of ground water was taken in a glass container along with the adsorbent and heated to the required temperature by placing it on a magnetic stirrer provided with hot plate at the agitation speed as per the experimental plan. The flow diagram of the experiment is given in Fig.1. The average fluoride ion concentration in groundwater was found to be 3.6 mg/L with a pH of 6.4. Table 1 summarizes the design of experimental runs (20) for removing fluoride ions in groundwater using non-doped and doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon. The fluoride removed from groundwater was calculated using Eq. 1.

$$\text{Fluoride percentage removal, } F = \frac{C_1 - C_2}{C_1} \times 100 \quad \dots (1)$$

Where, C_1 is the initial value of fluoride concentration in mg/L before treatment and C_2 is the final value of fluoride concentration in mg/L, after treatment with both non-doped and doped boron *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon prepared from sawdust.

Fig. 1. Treatment of groundwater using *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon

Table 1. Design of experimental runs

Runs	Particle size, μm	Adsorbent dosage, g/l	Agitation speed, rpm	Temperature, $^{\circ}\text{C}$
1	600	1	150	35
2	600	2	250	40
3	600	3	350	45
4	600	4	450	50
5	500	5	550	55
6	500	1	250	35
7	500	2	150	40
8	500	3	450	45
9	425	4	350	50
10	425	5	550	55
11	425	1	350	35
12	425	2	450	40
13	300	3	550	45
14	300	4	150	50
15	300	5	250	55
16	300	1	550	35
17	150	2	450	40
18	150	3	350	45
19	150	4	250	50
20	150	5	150	55

2.4. Surface Characteristics of Activated Carbon

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was employed to examine the surface morphology and pore network of non-doped and boron-doped activated carbon produced from sawdust of *Pterocarpus marsupium*. Prior to imaging, samples were dried, mounted on conductive stubs, and sputter-coated with a thin metal layer to prevent charging. Imaging was done at multiple magnifications to capture both overall particle texture and finer pore features. SEM provides

detailed visualization of morphological characteristics such as pore opening size, distribution uniformity, surface roughness, network connectivity, and structural integrity. Observations of the non-doped carbon reveal a baseline structure with irregular, less interconnected pores. Boron-doped samples display more uniformly distributed micropores and mesopores, indicating enhanced accessible surface and improved diffusion pathways. SEM micrographs also allow assessment of structural integrity, including the absence of collapsed walls or fractures, and reveal surface heterogeneities

introduced by boron incorporation. These observations explain differences in adsorption performance between the non-doped and boron-doped materials.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) of fluoride removal percentages for non-doped and boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon were computed from 20 runs per group at 95% confidence level using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) (Sivakumar *et al.*, 2018). An independent-sample t-test compared mean removal efficiencies between the two adsorbent types, with a two-tailed significance level set at $p < 0.05$. The T-test yielded the mean difference, standard error, and 95% confidence interval for the difference, providing both statistical significance and optimal parameter value. These results demonstrate whether boron incorporation produces a reliably higher fluoride removal performance under the specified experimental conditions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Surface Morphology Analysis of Non-Doped and Boron-Doped Carbon Structures

Experiments were conducted to study the percentage of fluoride removal in groundwater using non-doped and boron-doped activated carbon produced from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust. The SEM offers comprehensive details such as pores, fissures, and cracks regarding the surface morphology of active carbon prepared from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust. Fig. 2a and 2b show the SEM image of non-doped and boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust-activated carbon, respectively. These images were captured with an Electron High Tension (EHT) of 20.00 kV, a Working Distance (WD) of 10.5 mm, and using the secondary electrons of type 1 (SE1) signal with the scale bar indicating a length of 20 μm .

The SEM images present a comparative analysis of non-boron-doped and boron-doped activated

carbon. The SEM image provides a detailed view of a sample at a magnification of 500 times (500X), revealing a heterogeneous mixture of irregularly shaped particles. Fig. 2a, depicting non-boron-doped activated carbon, shows a heterogeneous microstructure characterized by irregularly shaped particles and a limited number of pores. This irregular distribution and smaller pore quantity indicate potential variability in material performance, affecting properties like adsorption capacity and structural strength. In contrast, Fig. 2b, featuring boron-doped activated carbon, reveals a more homogeneous microstructure with a significantly higher number of well-defined pores. The boron doping process appears to enhance the uniformity and porosity of the material, potentially increasing its surface area and improving its adsorption efficiency. This comparison highlights the impact of boron doping on the microstructural properties of activated carbon, demonstrating how the introduction of boron atoms can create a more uniform and porous material, which is advantageous for applications requiring high adsorption capacity and consistent material performance.

3.2. Fluoride Removal Efficiency Assessment

Fig. 3 presents the fluoride percentage removal in groundwater using non-doped activated carbon prepared from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust. Accordingly, Fig. 4 presents fluoride ion percentage removal in groundwater using boron-doped activated carbon prepared from novel *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon. The results of Fig. 3 demonstrate a consistent and significant reduction in fluoride concentration using non-doped activated carbon, with removal efficiencies ranging from 75% to 93.8%. The mean removal efficiency was 82.4%, with a standard deviation of 3.4%, indicating moderate variability across experimental trials. These findings confirm the effectiveness of non-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium*-derived activated carbon in fluoride adsorption under varying operational parameters. The results of Fig. 4 demonstrate a

consistent and significant reduction in fluoride concentration using boron-doped activated carbon, with removal efficiencies ranging from 88.1% to 97.5%. The mean removal efficiency was 92.3%, with a standard deviation of 2.1%, indicating high performance and low variability

across the experimental trials. These findings validate the enhanced adsorption capability of boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium*-based activated carbon in removing fluoride from groundwater.

a. Non-doped activated carbon

b. Boron-doped activated carbon

Fig. 2. Micro images of activated carbon produced from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust

Fig. 3. Fluoride removal percentage in groundwater using non-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon

As shown in Figs. 3 and 4, the fluoride percentage removal in groundwater was higher in boron-doped activated carbon compared to non-doped activated carbon prepared from novel *Pterocarpus marsupium*. The highest percentage of fluoride removal in groundwater was greater (97.5%) with the boron-doped activated carbon

prepared from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust than non-doped activated carbon (93.8%), both at optimum process values of 600 μm , 4 g, 450 rpm, and 50°C for particle size, dosage, speed, and temperature with a contact time of 60 min (Run 4). For the statistical analysis, the sample data were taken from the optimized parameters.

Fig. 4. Fluoride removal percentage in groundwater using boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon

The comparative analysis of Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 illustrates the superior fluoride removal performance of boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium*-based activated carbon over the non-doped variant, attributed to improvements in multiple physicochemical properties. Boron doping enhances the surface area of the activated carbon, providing more accessible sites for fluoride interaction and increasing overall adsorption efficiency compared to the relatively lower surface availability in the non-doped material. The pore structure of the boron-doped adsorbent is more uniform and better developed, with increased micropore and mesopore volumes that facilitate efficient diffusion and entrapment of fluoride ions. In contrast, the non-doped carbon exhibits a less organized pore distribution,

limiting fluoride accessibility and retention. Additionally, boron incorporation introduces electron-deficient sites that create stronger electrostatic attractions with negatively charged fluoride ions, resulting in a greater number of reactive adsorption sites and higher selectivity. The non-doped form, lacking these modifications, shows reduced affinity for fluoride and increased variability in performance. The enhanced stability and reproducibility observed in the boron-doped adsorbent, reflected in its higher mean removal efficiency and lower standard deviation, can also be linked to its improved interaction with key operational parameters, such as contact time, adsorbent dosage, agitation speed, and temperature, as outlined in the experimental design (Table 1). These combined effects

demonstrate that boron doping significantly improves the adsorptive characteristics and operational reliability of activated carbon for fluoride remediation in groundwater.

3.3. Effect of Process Parameters on Fluoride Adsorption

In this study, when the activated carbon material is used for treatment to remove fluoride at different process parameters, such as different particle sizes (600, 500, 425, 300, and 150 μm), adsorbent dosages (1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 g), agitation speeds (150, 250, 350, 450, and 550 rpm), and temperatures (35, 40, 45, 50, and 55°C), the boron-doped activated carbon appears to perform significantly better than non-doped activated carbon (Fig. 4). Understanding the surface morphology is crucial, as it impacts the total adsorption capacity of activated carbon and the surface area that may be used for adsorption. From Figs. 2a and 2b, it could be noted that the pore area is higher in the case of boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust-activated carbon than in the case of non-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust-activated carbon. This result also coincides with the fluoride removal efficiency from groundwater using both doped (Fig. 4) and non-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust activated carbon (Fig. 4). From Fig. 3, it may be found that there could be not much difference among various experimental runs from 1 to 20, except experimental run 4, in which this study obtained the maximum removal of fluoride using non-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust activated carbon. Whereas, from Fig. 4, it could be found that there was a fluoride removal percentage change among the various experimental runs, except for experimental run 4. The reason for the variation in fluoride removal percentage using *Pterocarpus marsupium*

sawdust-activated carbon is due to the increased active sites on *Pterocarpus marsupium*-activated carbon by boron ions. From Figs. 2a and 2b, it may be noted that the fluoride ion removal percentage depends on the usage of process parameters. The study's Fisher value, which is 3.15 at a significant p-value of 0.0001, shows that the fluoride percentage removal using non-doped and boron-doped novel *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon differs significantly from one another.

3.4. Statistical Evaluation of Adsorption Performance

Table 2 summarizes and compares the descriptive statistics of fluoride removal efficiencies for non-doped and boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon, providing the basis for statistical inference regarding their performance differences. From Table 2, it can be observed that the boron-doped activated carbon derived from *Pterocarpus marsupium* sawdust exhibits a higher mean fluoride removal efficiency along with a lower standard deviation and standard error of the mean compared to the non-doped variant. These statistical indicators suggest not only improved performance but also greater consistency and reliability in adsorption behavior. The results of the independent samples T-test further confirm that the differences between the two groups are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This highlights the beneficial effect of boron doping, which likely enhances the surface functionality and structural properties of the activated carbon, thereby increasing its affinity for fluoride ions. Consequently, boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon emerges as a promising and efficient material for fluoride remediation in groundwater treatment.

Table 2. Statistical comparison of performance of activated carbon

Group	Total Samples	Mean (%)	SD	SE to Mean
Boron Non-doped	20	82.4	3.4	0.66
Boron-doped	20	92.3	2.1	0.37

The results of independent sample T-test between non-doped and boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon for the removal of fluoride in groundwater are presented in Table 3. From Table 3, it may be noted that the lower and higher 95% confidence interval of the mean difference is between -11.782 and -7.704 with the dF value is 38 when equal variances are assumed between the two groups. The p-value between non-doped and boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon is 0.0001 ($p < 0.05$).

3.5. Comparison with Previous Studies

This comparative study demonstrates the transformative effects of boron doping on microstructural and adsorption properties. Prior research underscores the efficacy of modified materials in enhancing fluoride removal from aqueous solutions, a trend supported by the results of this study. Boron-doped activated carbon achieved fluoride removal efficiencies of 88.1% to 97.5%, significantly outperforming non-doped

activated carbon, which achieved 75% to 93.8%. Following each contact period, the treated water, which contained non-doped and boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon, was preserved for a full day without being altered and then filtered with filter paper. Previous studies also observed that the maximum removal of fluoride ions in groundwater depends on the contact time (Bakhta *et al.*, 2022), and the largest amount of fluoride removed from filtered groundwater occurred at a contact duration of 60 minutes (Sivakumar *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, a 9% increase in the percentage of fluoride removed from groundwater on boron-doped activated carbon is evident; in contrast, the percentage of fluoride removed from non-doped activated carbon was determined to be 97.5% (Sivakumar *et al.*, 2018). In line with research results, the mean accuracy of boron-doped activated carbon is higher than that of non-doped activated carbon, although the boron-doped activated carbon's standard deviation is somewhat higher.

Table 3. Independent sample T-test between non-doped and boron-doped activated carbon produced from *Pterocarpus marsupium*

Particulars	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		T-test for Equality of Means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
	F	P	T	dF	Mean Difference	SE Difference	Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	3.15	0.0001	-9.76	38	-9.743	0.9985	-11.782	-7.704

Note: F – Levene's test statistic for equality of variances; P – Significance level (p-value); T – t-test statistic; dF – Degrees of freedom; SE Difference – Standard Error of the Difference; Lower and Upper – Lower and Upper bounds of the 95% Confidence Interval for the Mean Difference; All values are calculated at a 95% confidence level and a p-value less than 0.05 indicates statistical significance.

This study demonstrated that boron-doped activated carbon achieved higher percentages of fluoride removal from groundwater, while non-doped activated carbon resulted in lower removal efficiencies. Similar results were reported in other studies, indicating that the percentage of fluoride removed from groundwater can be controlled by using different types of adsorbents. However, applying temperatures and extending the fluoride removal periods may lead to longer removal times or increased costs. Therefore, this study recommends further research to determine the efficacy of prepared activated carbon, by examining its characteristics. Consistent with these findings, Tolkou *et al.* (2021a) and Turki *et al.* (2023) reported that polymer- and zeolite-modified membranes exhibit enhanced adsorption kinetics and capacity, achieving fluoride removal efficiencies exceeding 90%. Similarly, Chufa *et al.* (2022) observed that graphene oxide nano adsorbents achieved fluoride removal rates of 93–97.5%, attributed to their increased surface area and functional adsorption sites. Patel and Bhasin (2023) support these findings, highlighting a 98.2% fluoride removal efficiency for graphene/Ce composites supported on activated carbon.

Material modifications are crucial for maintaining consistent performance under varying environmental conditions, as reviewed by Dantie *et al.* (2019). For example, advanced materials like iron oxide nanoparticles modified with ionic liquids achieved 91.6% fluoride removal (Pillai *et al.*, 2020), while zirconium-impregnated anion exchange resins demonstrated efficiencies exceeding 90% (Singh *et al.*, 2020). Akafu *et al.* (2019) achieved over 89% fluoride removal using aluminium hydroxide-modified diatomite, and Yapo *et al.* (2022) demonstrated efficiencies of 95.6% with hydroxyapatite-modified materials. Furthermore, Wei *et al.* (2022) and Wan *et al.* (2021) reviewed composite adsorbents and their synergistic interactions, which could be extended to boron doping. This

study's high fluoride removal efficiency aligns with their findings on enhanced functional site formation and adsorption capacity. For example, Lin *et al.* (2021) observed fluoride degradation efficiencies of 94% using photocatalytic systems, while Ogata *et al.* (2020) demonstrated hydroxide-based materials removing fluoride at rates of 90–95%. Affordable and scalable methods like electrocoagulation reported by Castañeda *et al.* (2021), achieving fluoride removal efficiencies of 85–92.0%, and cellulose-based adsorbents discussed by Tolkou *et al.* (2021b), with removal rates exceeding 88%, could complement high-performing materials such as boron-doped activated carbon. These synergies could enable broader accessibility and sustainability in addressing fluoride contamination in drinking water.

3.6. Optimizing Fluoride Removal using Boron-Doped Carbon

This study investigates the impact of boron doping on the fluoride adsorption performance of *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon. Through a detailed analysis of key operational factors, it highlights the enhanced efficiency and stability of the doped material.

3.6.1. Effect of particle size

Particle size plays a critical role in determining the external surface area and diffusion path length available for fluoride ions. Across a wide particle size range, boron-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon consistently demonstrated superior removal efficiency compared to its non-doped counterpart. This enhanced performance is attributed to the optimized pore structure and greater density of active sites in the doped material, which reduce diffusion constraints. The ability of boron-doped carbon to maintain high efficiency even with coarser particle sizes indicates its reduced dependence on precise size control.

3.6.2. Effect of adsorbent dosage

The dosage of activated carbon affects the total number of available adsorption sites. Both adsorbents showed improved fluoride removal with increasing dosage; however, boron-doped carbon achieved high performance at relatively lower dosages. This implies a stronger inherent affinity for fluoride ions, leading to more efficient usage of material. Moreover, the doped carbon demonstrated more consistent results across different dosages, confirming its reliability and economic advantage in practical applications.

3.6.3. Effect of Agitation Speed

Agitation speed influences the rate of mass transfer between the aqueous phase and the adsorbent surface. Boron-doped carbon maintained high fluoride removal even at moderate agitation levels, while the performance of non-doped carbon was more sensitive to increased mixing. This difference suggests that the doped variant possesses improved pore connectivity and more accessible active sites, allowing it to function effectively under less intensive mixing conditions.

3.6.4. Effect of Temperature

Temperature affects both diffusion kinetics and adsorption equilibrium. Both materials showed enhanced performance with moderate temperature increases. However, boron-doped carbon exhibited greater thermal stability and less variability in removal efficiency across the tested temperature range. This indicates that the fluoride binding on the doped surface is more thermodynamically favourable, making it more robust under varying environmental temperatures.

This study presents a comprehensive evaluation of boron-doped versus non-doped *Pterocarpus marsupium* activated carbon for fluoride removal from groundwater. Key operational parameters, including particle size, dosage, agitation speed, and temperature, were systematically assessed. Morphological analysis using SEM, combined

with statistical validation, confirmed that boron doping significantly enhances the adsorption performance. The doped carbon demonstrated superior fluoride removal efficiency, improved consistency across varying environmental conditions, and outperformed many advanced modified materials reported in the literature. These findings highlight the novelty and potential of boron-doped activated carbon as a cost-effective, robust, and scalable solution for groundwater defluoridation with promising applicability in hybrid treatment systems.

4. CONCLUSIONS

From the comparison of non-boron-doped and boron-doped activated carbon produced from *Pterocarpus marsupium* saw dust, it is found that boron doping significantly enhanced both structural and adsorption performances. SEM imaging revealed that non-boron-doped activated carbon exhibited irregularly shaped particles with limited pores, contributing to higher fluoride removal efficiencies ranging from 75% to 93.8%, with variability likely caused by inconsistent binding sites. In contrast, boron-doped activated carbon displayed a uniform microstructure with increased porosity, achieving consistently higher fluoride removal efficiencies between 88.1% and 97.5%. The enhanced performance of the boron-doped variant is attributed to the introduction of additional functional sites, improved surface area, and increased affinity for fluoride ions. Even under less optimal conditions, the boron-doped material maintained superior efficiency, with its lowest removal rate surpassing the highest achieved by the non-doped variant. These findings affirm that boron doping of activated carbon produced from *Pterocarpus marsupium* saw dust, makes it a highly effective and reliable material for water treatment applications for fluoride removal. Future research should focus on optimizing the boron doping process and exploring its scalability for practical implementation.

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